

Dear Nouri,

I have just returned from several weeks in Africa and I am having to catch up with the work which has accumulated in my absence, both in the Department and in the family.

I will finish my reading of your book shortly and I shall then write to you immediately giving my impressions and views.

I hope all is well with you.

Thank you very much indeed for the beautiful backgammon set which you gave me, it is almost too nice to play with.

Colette joins me in sending her warmest greetings.

Yours sincerely,

Kevin

The University of Sheffield

Faculty of Pure Science

Dean: Professor Kevin Connolly

Sheffield S10 2TN
Tel: Sheffield 768555 Ext.
STD code: 0742

12.12.88

Dear Nouri,

I have just returned from several weeks in Africa and am hurrying to catch up with the work which has accumulated in my absence, both in the Department and in the Faculty.

I will finish my reading of your book shortly and I shall then write to you immediately giving my impressions and views.

I hope all is well with you. Thank you very much indeed for the beautiful Backgammon set which you gave me, it is almost too nice to play with.

Colette joins me in sending her warmest greetings.

Yours sincerely,

Kevin